

FINAL REPORT

1 General Information

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Project title: COPFUN: Biologische und chemische Diversität der koprophilen Pilze, mit besonderem Fokus auf der Taxonomie der Sordariales

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2 Summary

New and interesting fungi have been isolated from dung, confirming it as a prolific substrate for uncovering new fungal biodiversity. Taxa belonging to the Sordariales were frequently recovered from this substrate, but also from soil, with additional strains obtained through collaborations for the study of their secondary metabolism. These fungi have proven to be prolific producers of secondary metabolites with diverse bioactivities. For instance, the potent cytotoxic compound neochetracin and the antifungal dactylfungins were discovered during the project. Another remarkable finding is the arcopilins, a novel metabolite family capable of disrupting preformed *Staphylococcus aureus* biofilms.

Over the course of the project, more than 200 strains belonging to the Sordariales have been tested for secondary metabolite production. These data are currently being used to identify new antimicrobial compounds and are further combined with omics-based technologies and bioactivity-guided pipelines to maximize the likelihood of discovery. Moreover, the dataset generated from this taxonomically studied group provides opportunities for broader investigations into fungal evolution, biosynthetic potential, and the ecological roles of secondary metabolites in relation to life strategies and microbial interactions.

Aus Dung wurden neue und interessante Pilze isoliert, was bestätigt, dass dies ein hochinteressantes Substrat für die Entdeckung neuer pilzlicher Biodiversität ist. Besonders pilzliche Taxa, die zu der Ordnung Sordariales gehören, wurden häufig aus diesem Substrat, aber auch aus dem Boden gewonnen, wobei zusätzliche Stämme über Kooperationen zur Untersuchung ihres Sekundärstoffwechsels beschafft wurden. Diese Pilze haben sich als talentierte Produzenten von Sekundärmetaboliten mit vielfältigen bioaktiven Eigenschaften erwiesen. So wurden im Rahmen des Projekts beispielsweise die potente zytotoxische Verbindung Neochetracin und die antimykotischen Dactylfungine entdeckt. Eine weitere bemerkenswerte Entdeckung sind die Arcopiline, eine neue Familie von Metaboliten, die in der Lage sind, vorgebildete Biofilme von *Staphylococcus aureus* zu zerstören.

Im Laufe des Projekts wurden mehr als 200 Stämme der Sordariales auf die Produktion von Sekundärmetaboliten getestet. Diese Daten werden derzeit zur Identifizierung neuer antimikrobieller Verbindungen genutzt und zusätzlich mit omics-basierten Technologien und bioaktivitätsgesteuerten Pipelines kombiniert, um die Wahrscheinlichkeit einer Entdeckung zu erhöhen. Darüber hinaus bieten die aus dieser taxonomisch untersuchten Gruppe generierten Daten die Möglichkeit für umfassendere Untersuchungen zur Evolution von Pilzen, ihrem

biosynthetischen Potenzial und zur ökologischen Rolle von Sekundärmetaboliten in Bezug auf Lebensstrategien und mikrobielle Interaktionen.

3 Progress Report

Background and objectives of the project

The COPFUN project focused on exploring the biological and chemical diversity of coprophilous fungi, i.e. fungi that inhabit or are associated with the animal dung, particularly that of herbivorous. Dung was selected as the research target because, compared to other substrates such as plants or soil, this remains a largely understudied niche. The project was driven by the hypothesis that dung represents a promising reservoir of new and interesting fungal biodiversity. A further motivation was the high potential of dung-inhabiting fungi to produce biologically active secondary metabolites, as this substrate constitutes a highly competitive environment where fungi employ such compounds as defense mechanisms against other microorganisms (Charria-Girón et al. 2025).

A specific emphasis was placed on members of the order Sordariales, common fungi found in dung, as the taxonomic placement of a high number of taxa remains unresolved at both species and higher taxonomic ranks (Marin-Felix et al. 2020, Marin-Felix and Miller 2022). Traditionally, classification of sordarialean fungi relied heavily on ascospore morphology, which was later proven to be of limited value for inferring phylogenetic relationships (Miller and Huhndorf 2005). Modern taxonomy recommends a polyphasic approach, combining morphological characteristics with molecular analysis. However, sequence data remains unavailable for many species due to the lack of material, making recollection efforts essential. At higher taxonomic levels, classification challenges are also evident. For instance, the family Lasiosphaeriaceae was historically considered polyphyletic since it was separated in different monophyletic lineages scattered along the order (Huhndorf et al. 2004). Although recent redefinitions have clarified some relationships, several family delimitations remain insufficiently supported (Marin-Felix and Miller 2022). Genomic data is expected to provide the phylogenetic backbone needed to establish a more natural and robust classification within the order.

Beyond taxonomy, members of the Sordariales have proven to be prolific producers of secondary metabolites with diverse bioactivities. The Chaetomiaceae is the most extensively studied family, with 189 compounds reported between 2016 and 2021 alone (Ibrahim et al. 2021). Other families remain poorly studied or even neglected, yet 174 bioactive compounds had been documented up to 2022 (Charria-Girón et al. 2022). Notable examples include

sordarins, a class of natural antifungal agents that inhibit protein synthesis in eukaryotes through their interaction with elongation factor 2 (eEF2) (Harms et al. 2021), and cytochalasans, a family of compounds that disrupt actin polymerization in eukaryotic cells (Valencia-Revelo et al. 2025). The latter group of metabolites has been the focus of another DFG-funded project within our research group, expecting to potentially find synergies between both projects.

Based on the above, the objectives of the project were:

- To isolate new and interesting coprophilous fungi in order to expand knowledge of untapped fungal biodiversity, which is of particular importance in the current context of global biodiversity loss affecting all groups of organisms. Special emphasis was given to the isolation of members of the Sordariales, with the aim of obtaining material for as many species as possible. This would enable the generation of sequence data and the performance of polyphasic studies, ultimately contributing to a more natural classification of the sordarialean taxa.
- To study the secondary metabolite production of coprophilous fungi, especially of sordarialean taxa, in order to discover bioactive compounds with potential as new drug candidates for anti-infective and other pharmaceutical indications. In addition, the biosynthetic potential of Sordariales was to be integrated into polyphasic studies, enabling chemotaxonomic analyses that would contribute to the taxonomic reassessment and reclassification of these fungi.
- To sequence 20 genomes of representative species of the Sordariales in order to perform phylogenomic analyses and achieve a more natural taxonomic classification of taxa in the order. This objective focused particularly on higher taxonomic ranks, with the aim of verifying the validity of several recently introduced but doubtful families.

Results and possible application perspectives and conceivable follow-up studies

During the project, over 300 strains were isolated from dung samples collected across different countries, including new taxa such as *Parascedosporium germanicum* and *Scytalidium essehofinum*, both of which are currently under review for publication in *Mycological Progress*. These findings underscore the potential of dung as a reservoir of novel fungal biodiversity. In addition, a substantial number of strains belonging to the Sordariales, which was the primary target for the taxonomic and secondary metabolism studies were isolated. Through collaborations with other laboratories, more than 100 additional strains were unexpectedly acquired, resulting in the largest collection of Sordariales to date. This abundance of promising

strains led us to focus exclusively on the biosynthetic potential of the Sordariales, rather than extending screening efforts to other Sordariomycetes from dung. Nevertheless, these taxa remain of interest for potential future screening for antimicrobial activity.

Over the three-year duration of the project, more than 200 fungal sordarialean strains have been tested for the secondary metabolite production on different solid and liquid media. Based on metabolomic analyses combined with bioassay results, we identified several promising strains as potential producers of new bioactive compounds and selected them for compound isolation. To date, 18 new compounds from sordarialean taxa have already been published (Charria-Girón et al. 2023b, 2024a,b, Harms et al. 2024, Barrera-Adame et al. 2025), while more than 10 additional compounds are currently under study and undergoing characterization. It should be noted that we are currently developing a pipeline that integrates metabolomics data with the bioactivity of crude extracts to predict strains producing potential new bioactive compounds. Additionally, these crude extracts will be tested against a broader panel of pathogens to increase the likelihood of discovering novel antimicrobial agents.

Among the most promising compounds found during the course of the project are the arcopilins, a novel family of PKS-NRPS metabolites able to disrupt preformed biofilms of *Staphylococcus aureus*, which causes chronic or fatal infection by forming biofilms on medical devices. Notably, arcopilin A enhances the activity of gentamicin and vancomycin by up to 115-fold and 31-fold, respectively (Charria-Girón et al. 2024b). Future follow-up studies could explore the potential of these compounds as part of conjugated treatment strategies.

Another relevant group of compounds under consideration is the dactylfungins, already recognized for their antifungal activity. We have identified a new sordarialean fungus, *Amesía hispanica*, which produces these compounds in high amounts, along with novel derivatives (Charria-Girón et al. 2023b). Given the growing concern of antifungal resistance, further exploration of these antifungal metabolites represents an important avenue for future research.

Finally, epithiodiketopiperazines, including chetracin B and the newly discovered neochetracin, were isolated and demonstrated strong cytotoxic activity. However, their potential therapeutic application is currently limited by inherent toxicity to both healthy and cancer cell lines (Charria-Girón et al. 2024a). Further studies aimed at elucidating their molecular mode of action and optimizing the chemical scaffold could represent an interesting avenue to overcome this limitation.

As mentioned before, several compounds have been already isolated and are under further evaluation. For instance, from a new described genus and combination, *Stchigelomyces brunnescens*, six new compounds with diverse bioactivities have been isolated and characterized. The corresponding manuscript has been recently submitted. Another example concerns the mycotoxins isolated from different species of *Staphylotrichum*, including new ones, which are being integrated into a chemotaxonomic study, given the significance of mycotoxin-producing genera. Another highlight is the discovery of two new antimicrobial compounds from a new species of *Zopfiella*, which are currently being fully characterized. We anticipate at least four additional publications describing new sordarialean taxa producing antimicrobial compounds.

In parallel, we have already obtained the genomes of four interesting strains, and the sequencing of an additional 12 strains is currently in progress. These data will serve as the basis for a phylogenomic study of the order, with the goal of resolving the taxonomic placement of several uncertain taxa (Marin-Felix and Miller 2022). This work is expected to be completed by mid-2026, thereby fulfilling the remaining objectives established for the current project.

As previously mentioned, the project was intended to create synergies with another DFG-funded project on cytochalasans. However, it was ultimately found that most members of the Chaetomiaceae did not produce this class of compounds. On the other hand, several guest students from Cameroon and Colombia under my supervision, in addition to working on dung-inhabiting fungi, also studied strains originating from their home countries. My preliminary identifications revealed that some of these strains belonged to the genus *Diaporthe*, a well-known producer of cytochalasans and a genus within the same class as the Sordariales, the Sordariomycetes. Consequently, the screening for bioactive compounds was directed towards these *Diaporthe* species. As a result, we were able to introduce five new species of *Diaporthe* and isolate more than ten compounds, including new bioactive metabolites (Charria-Girón et al. 2023a, Lambert et al. 2023, Matio Kemkuignou et al. 2023). Following the same principle, another sordariomycete fungus from Colombia identified as *Xylaria* sp. was selected for screening, resulting in the isolation of five cytochalasans along with other bioactive compounds (Valencia-Revelo et al. 2025).

All data generated during the project have been made openly available. Publications were released in open access journals. Strains were deposited in leading biodiversity repositories, and their sequence data were submitted to GenBank. In addition, the results of the project were disseminated at both international and national scientific conferences, including the International Mycological Congress (IMC12) in the Netherlands, the Asian Mycological

Congress 2023 (AMC 2023) in Korea, and the 100th anniversary of the German Mycological Society (DGfM) congress in Germany.

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4 Published Project Results

4.1 Category A – Articles in peer-reviewed journals, contributions to peer-reviewed conferences or to anthology volumes, and book publications

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4.2 Category B – Any other form of published results: N/A

4.3 Patents (applied for and granted): N/A